

ISic3007

I.Sicily inscription 3007

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

graffiti

Material

limestone (local)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Contrada Furmica, c.7km to south

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Antiquarium di Akrai
(?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333354

1. ν AI vac.
2. θρασὺς (?) vac.
3. #⁵⁶ κατάπυγο ς
4. Ὠνότορ vac.
5. ΚΑΜΙΜΑΔΕΟΣ vac.
6. [—].ΟΣ.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645356

EDCS 70900724

PHI 333354

Bibliography

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